

Appendix

A. Replication on a Larger Time Window

Build time. Table III shows that Bazel outperforms Go Build at parallelism settings of 1–16 for both full and incremental builds. For full builds, Bazel required 122.3 minutes at the parallelism setting of one versus 155.5 minutes for Go Build, and 15.1 vs. 19.2 minutes at the parallelism setting of eight. When parallelism is set to 32, however, the tools achieve similar performance (8.4 vs. 8.9 minutes). Incremental builds follow the same pattern, i.e., Bazel is faster at parallelism settings of 1–16 (e.g., 77.3 vs. 109.7 minutes at parallelism of 1; 9.1 vs. 10.4 minutes at parallelism of 16), but performance becomes comparable at the parallelism setting of 32 (8.0 vs. 8.3 minutes). Compared to our original study (Section III in the paper), these findings confirm Observations 1 and 2 (O1, O2), yet highlight that the gap at high parallelism settings is now narrowed. We conjecture that this shift is due to the evolution of the Kubernetes codebase; its larger dependency graph and restructured modules increase the coordination overhead of Bazel’s DAG-based scheduling, while making Go Build’s simpler package-level concurrency relatively more effective at our maximum studied parallelism setting of 32.

Resource consumption. Table IV shows that Bazel consistently consumes more memory than Go Build. For full builds, Bazel required 22.3 GiB at the parallelism setting of two compared to Go Build’s 5.4 GiB, and at the maximum studied setting of 32, Bazel still used more than four times more memory (24.1 vs. 5.5 GiB). For incremental builds, Bazel’s memory footprint ranged from 4.9 GiB at a parallelism setting of one to 5.8 GiB at the parallelism setting of 32, while Go Build remained between 2.4–1.8 GiB. CPU utilization shows contrasting patterns. For full builds, Bazel scaled proportionally with parallelism (951% at the parallelism setting of 16, and 935% at 32), whereas Go Build saturated workers less aggressively (889% at the parallelism setting of 16, 833% at 32). For incremental builds, Bazel’s CPU usage grows substantially (1,451% at the parallelism setting of 16, and 1,642% at 32), whereas Go Build’s CPU usage remained far lower (301% and 290% at parallelism settings of 16 and 32, respectively). Despite its lower resource usage, Go Build did not translate these savings into faster builds except at the maximum studied parallelism setting of 32.

TABLE III: Median build times (minutes) across 14 commits.

Par.	Full		Incremental	
	Bazel	Go	Bazel	Go
1	122.3	155.5	77.3	109.7
2	61.0	80.0	43.6	60.6
4	26.7	38.4	23.9	24.2
8	15.1	19.2	12.7	14.4
16	10.6	12.2	9.1	10.4
32	8.4	8.9	8.0	8.3

TABLE IV: Median CPU utilization (%) and memory consumption (GiB) across 14 commits.

Par.	Full				Incremental			
	CPU		Memory		CPU		Memory	
	Bazel	Go	Bazel	Go	Bazel	Go	Bazel	Go
1	100.2	100.5	20.5	5.3	100.0	100.1	4.9	2.4
2	200.5	201.1	22.3	5.4	200.2	192.9	5.2	2.1
4	401.6	402.0	21.3	5.5	400.8	283.9	5.0	2.1
8	722.1	712.0	19.5	5.5	802.0	311.4	3.6	2.0
16	951.3	888.6	21.7	5.6	1,451.3	300.6	4.1	1.8
32	935.1	832.6	24.1	5.5	1,641.9	290.2	5.8	1.8

TABLE IV: Feature-to-observation mapping contrasting artifact-based (e.g., Bazel/Buck/Pants) and language-specific tools (e.g., Go Build/Maven).

Feature	Artifact-based (Bazel/Buck/Pants)	Language-specific (Go Build/Maven)	Effect on Observations
DAG and parallelism	Fine-grained task DAG; wide parallel scheduling; exploits many cores	No global DAG; coarse dependency tracking; limited parallelism	Artifact-based tools achieve faster full builds (O1) and incremental builds at high parallelism (O2); language-specific tools are slower as scale increases
Aggressive caching	Local and remote artifact caching; content-hash reuse (e.g., RuleKeys)	Local-only caching; narrower reuse scope	Artifact-based tools speed up incremental builds significantly at scale (O2); language-specific tools show weaker gains
Dependency graph overhead (memory)	Constructs and stores fine-grained graph state; caching increases footprint with project size	No global graph kept in memory; resolves per module; lower baseline memory	Artifact-based tools consume more memory (O3); language-specific tools remain lighter
Worker process model (CPU)	Many workers/processes for fine-grained parallelism; higher CPU load at scale	Fewer processes; limited concurrency; lower CPU but capped scalability	Artifact-based tools use more CPU at scale in both full (O4) and incremental (O5) builds; language-specific tools use less CPU but plateau earlier